

Service Quality Level and The Perception of Customers: A Study on Nijhoom Tours – 5* rated travel and tourism company in Bangladesh

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Abstract: *The study investigates and measure the service quality level of Nijhoom - through SERVQUAL-model statements that means that we measure customer expectations and customer perceptions and make a comparison between different areas of service given by the organization. To do this Five-Point Likert Scale has been used to survey on tourists. The study actually reveals the state of service quality level and the customer perception on this service and whether the service quality level, its standard and customer perceptions are able to increase market share in the industry and be able to make a strong brand image. The current study aims to analyze the performances of The Nijhoom Tours by focusing on the SERVQUAL dimensions. The main purpose of the study is to measure the service quality level of customers and their perceived value of the services given by the Nijhoom Tours. The study also has the objective to find out and analyze the service gaps.as well as on the basis of service gaps and other findings, a comprehensive recommendation will be given. The study found that different service quality and dimensions bound customers to perceive service quality differently and its service quality level is moderate though it is leading company in the country. So the company should analyze the customer expectations first and then it should make a diagram so that the company can give the best services to the customers.*

Keyword: *Service Quality Dimension, Tourists Behavioral Patterns, Sustainable Tourism, Public-Private Partnership, Competitive Advantage. Customer expectations, Customers satisfaction, Customer perceptions, SERVQUAL-model.*

1. Introduction and the Significance of the Topic

Now this is a competitive, constant changing and information age world, where past is replaced by dynamic present and the dynamic present is being replaced by more challenging future, the old ways of doing things is no longer valid. Change is a reality and continuous process. Those who are not able to keep pace with the changes are destined to lose the race. Tourism is emerging as a leading global economic driver for the 21st century. It has enormous potential as a catalyst for future economic and social development. So the tourism sector in Bangladesh has enormous potentials for economic and social development.

Service quality is needed for creating customer satisfaction and service quality is connected to customer perceptions and customer expectations. Oliver (1997) argues that service quality can be described as the result from customer comparisons between their expectations about the service they will use and their perceptions about the service company. That means that if the perceptions would be higher than the expectations the service will be considered excellent, if the expectations equal the perceptions the service is considered good and if the expectations are not met the service will be considered bad.

Oliver (1997) argues that customer satisfaction can be described as a judgment that a product or service feature, or the product or service itself, provides pleasurable consumption. Satisfaction can also be described as a fulfillment response of service and an attitude change as a result of the consumption. Gibson (2005) put forward that satisfied customers are likely to become loyal customers and that means that they are also likely to spread positive word of mouth. Understanding which factors that influence customer satisfaction makes it easier to design and deliver service offers that corresponds to the market demands. Service quality linked explicitly to customer satisfaction that marketer too seen as having an important role to play.

Making service processes more efficient does not necessarily result in a better quality experience for customers, or does it always lead to improved benefits for them. Likewise, but at other times it may sometimes be welcomed by customers, but at other times it may make them feel rushed and unwanted.

Marketing's interest in service quality is obvious when one thinks about it. Poor quality places a firm at a competitive disadvantage, potentially driving away-dissatisfied customers. Customer satisfaction, a term frequently used in marketing, is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet surpass expectation. Customer satisfaction is defined as "the number of customers, or percentage of total customers, whose reported experience with a firm, its products, or its services (ratings) exceeds specified satisfaction goals. Customer satisfaction provides a leading indicator of consumer purchase intentions and loyalty. "Management must think of itself not as producing products but as proving customer creating value satisfaction. "Customer satisfaction has a vital role in sustaining and improving the whole on the market.

The customers always think negatively towards marketing. Sometimes they do not want to realize the power and strength of modern marketing forces in the service oriented business. Tourism services are intangible. The rationale of the study lies in the fact as the provision of high quality service aids in meeting several requirements such as customer satisfaction and its consequent loyalty and market share, acquiring new customers, improved productivity, and financial performance and profitability of the firm. It has also become an important research topic because of its important relationship to corporate marketing and the perception of customers. In the current study we will try to find out the customer service performance of Nijhoom Tours Limited. This piece of research effort will be helpful for the tourism entrepreneurs, researchers, and policy makers.

2. Research Objectives:

- The main purpose of the study is to measure the service quality level and identify perceived value from the customers' points of view of Nijhoom Tours.
- To prescribe some suggestions for the improvement of service quality of the company.

3. Research Methodology

1. Research Approach:

- This is a quantitative research, in some cases qualitative approach has been applied.
- At first phase an exploratory research has been conducted to understand the nature of problem and its subcomponents.

2. Sources of Data

To meet the research objectives both primary and secondary sources of data have been used. More emphasis is given on primary data to conduct the research program authentically.

a. Primary Source:

1. A model questionnaire has been developed to elicit essential data. The Questionnaire is structured in nature and is based on Likert Scale method.

Population: All Customers of Nijhoom Tours (approximate 2200 customers)

Sampling technique: Convenience sampling technique was used to select specific students who are the regular tourists of the company.

Sample Size: Total of 100 Customers.

Survey area: Dhaka

2. Informal interviews with tourist experts and managers of Nijhoom Tours.
3. Observation of tourists while taking services.

b. Secondary Sources:

- Books and articles on service quality levels
- Various websites

Data Analysis Techniques:

- Excel and SPSS software has been used to analyze data
- Various statistical methods and formulae has been used.
- Different Graphs, Tables, Charts and others instruments are used to make presentable the research results (Findings).

4. Theoretical Framework of the Study

Service Quality

From the viewpoint of business administration, "Service Quality is an achievement in customer service. It reflects at each service encounter. Customers form service expectations from experiences, word of mouth and advertisement. In general, Customers compare perceived service with expected service in which if the former falls short of the latter the customers are disappointed".

The measurement of subjective aspects of customer service depends on the conformity of the expected benefit with the perceived result. This in turns depends upon the customer's expectation in terms of service, they might receive and the service provider's ability and talent to present this expected service. Successful Companies add benefits to their offering that not only satisfy the customers but also surprise and delight them. Delighting customers is a matter of exceeding their expectations.

Pre-defined objective criteria may be unattainable in practice, in which case, the best possible achievable result becomes the ideal. The objective ideal may still be poor, in subjective terms.

Service quality can be related to service potential (for example, worker's qualifications); service process (for example, the quickness of service) and service result (customer satisfaction).

Importance of Service Quality

The importance of service has obtained a significant amount of attention by many managers and academic scholars in a variety of fields. Identifying the nature of the relationship between service quality and relevant constructs appears to be advantageous as it assists in the development of better managerial decisions. This realization is reflected by the increasing number of publications devoted to such topics as customer satisfaction, service quality, customer service, and service marketing . Prior to discussing the concept of service quality and its relationships with other constructs, it is necessary to be concerned with the three fundamental characteristics of a service product. In these circumstances it is very important to pay attention to study of service quality, its dimensions and measuring method in order to improve it continuously. Continuous offer of high quality service is extremely important to reach consumer satisfaction, which is reflected positively to competition and to profitable business of service companies. [Sources: Website, Zeithaml, V.A., Parasuraman, A. and Berry, L.L.(1990), Delivering quality service; Balancing customer perceptions and expectations, The Free Press, New York, NY]

Measuring of Service Quality

Measuring the quality of a service can be a very difficult exercise. Unlike product where there are specific specifications such as length, depth, width, weight, color etc. a service can have numerous intangible or qualitative specifications. In addition, there is there expectation of the customer with regards the service, which can vary considerably based on a range of factors such as prior experience, personal needs and what other people may have told them.

Method of analysis

To analyze the result we use the SERVQUAL- model statements (Parasuraman et al, (1990). That means that we measure customer expectations and customer perceptions and make a comparison between different areas of service. Each answer alternative is given a score and the score for expectations is summarized and the score for perceptions is summarized. Then the difference between expectations and perceptions is counted and a judgment about the service quality is given. The overall service quality level is showed through counting the score of each dimension and then summarize them. Jannadi and Al Saggaf (2000) explains that the calculation shows a gap between perceptions and expectations and through that gap the service will be evaluated through the following formula.

n_i

$$\sum P_i - E_i = 1$$

$$SQ_i (\text{feature}) = P_i - E_i \quad (1)$$

$$SQ (\text{dimension}) = (-) \rightarrow 1/n \quad (2)$$

When n = number of items in the dimension

$$\text{Overall } SQ = \sum 1/n \quad (3)$$

When n = total number of features

i = each feature

SQ = Service Quality

P = Perception score

E = Expectation score

Standard deviations are also used to measure dispersion of data around the mean. To be able to analyze the different answer options we gave each option different points, this method is called Likert scale. The expectations and perceptions are evaluated through 22 statements and the answer options are rated through five point Likert scale. The result is also linked with theory to identify which areas the company should improve. We used Microsoft Excel to transform the raw data from the questionnaires into diagrams and tables that are easier to facilitate.

Parasuraman later revises the SERVQUAL model, where the differences are shown as follows:

1. Firstly, the term "should" in its original version may lead to unrealistically high results related to expectations, so the new model introduces somewhat different terms. Revised terms focus on what users' expectations should be from the company that delivers excellent service. For example, item "City Public Transportation should have accurate timetable", has been modified into an item "Distinctive public transportation in the city will insist on accurate timetable".
2. Secondly, all negative items' formulation in an original version of the SERVQUAL is changed by positive formulation. For example, "The employees of XYZ are not always willing to help users", has been changed into "Employees are not always willing to help you".
3. Thirdly, two original items, one within the perceptibility, and another one within the safety, have been changed by two new ones that explain dimensions in a better way: perceptibility and safety.
4. In the fourth place, evaluation of significance of each of five dimensions in original model is gained indirectly by regressive analysis. Revised model introduces the third set of questions for users that directly measures relative significance of each of five dimensions for users. These results are then used to evaluate the indicator of each dimension of perceptive service quality. The main purpose is to obtain the most accurate result of perceptive service quality.

Various Dimensions of Service Quality

A Customer's expectation of a particular service is determined by factors such as recommendations, personal needs and experiences. The expected service and the perceived service sometimes may not be equal, thus leaving a gap. The service quality model or the 'GAP model' developed by a group of authors- Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry at Texas and North Carolina in 1985, highlights the main requirements for delivering high service quality. It identifies five 'gaps' that cause unsuccessful delivery. Customers generally have a tendency to compare the service they 'experience' with the service they 'expect'. If the experience does not match the expectation, there arises a gap. Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry described ten determinants that may influence the appearance of a gap. in the SERVQUAL model: reliability, responsiveness, competence, access, courtesy, communication, credibility, security, understanding the customer and tangibles.

Later, the determinants were reduced to five: tangibles; reliability; responsiveness; service assurance and empathy in the so-called RATER model.

Found that the following ten dimensions affect expectations and perception of service quality:

1. Reliability
2. Sensibility
3. Competitiveness
4. Accessibility
5. Politeness
6. Communicability
7. Credibility
8. Safety
9. Understanding and consumer commitment
10. Tangibility

[Sources: MA.Parasuraman,A.,Zeithaml,V.A.andBerry,L.L.(1988),"SERVQUAL: a multi-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of the service quality ",Journal of Retailing,Vol.64,No.1,pp.12-40.]

Later development of a model for measuring service quality brought Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry to a conclusion that awareness solution is more acceptable for above-mentioned ten dimensions converted into the following five ones:

1. Tangibility (physical objects, equipment, appearance of service staff)
2. Reliability (potential to deliver a promised service)
3. Sensitivity (willingness to help consumers and to provide fast service)
4. Safety (knowledge and politeness of the staff and their capability of getting trust)

5. Empathy (care, individual attention for consumers)

Safety and empathy represent in fact seven original quality dimensions: competitiveness, accessibility, politeness, communicability, credibility, safety and understanding and commitment for consumers. Reducing number of dimensions has not reduced accuracy in quality measurement.

It is obvious that there are different opinions on dimensions of service quality. It would be hard to extinguish some of above approaches as the most acceptable in explanation and understanding the essence of perceived service quality; however, when speaking on quality measurement the Parasuraman’s concept of five dimensions is mostly used.

Maintaining Service Quality:

After having attained the desired service level, the next great challenge faced by service providers is to maintain service standards at levels of excellence. This is as important, and as tough, as establishing service standards and attaining to them in the first place. There are two approaches that any organization can have towards maintaining service standards - a proactive approach or a reactive approach.

Proactive: A proactive approach entails actively reaching out to customers and trying to gather their feedback on service quality and suggested areas of improvement. This can be done by way of

- Surveys and administering questionnaires
- Gap Analysis, and
- Staff training

1. **Surveys and questionnaires:** Such an approach helps a brand to anticipate customer demands and expectations and align its service offering accordingly. In addition, the findings of such surveys can help to identify common issues and demands of customers hence helping a company to customize its service offering.
2. **Gap Analysis:** Another approach that is adopted for analyzing service quality is that of the gap analysis. The company has an ideal service standard that it would like to offer to its customers. This is contrasted with the current level of service being offered. The gap thus identified serves both as a measure and as a basis for planning a future course of action to improve the service offering.
3. **Staff Training:** Another crucial aspect of the proactive approach is staff training. Companies nowadays spend generously on training their personnel to adequately handle customer queries and/or complaints. This is particularly true if a company is changing its service offering or going in for a price hike of its existing services. For example, when a fast food chain increases the price of its existing products, the staff has to handle multiple customer queries regarding the hike. Lack of a satisfactory explanation would signify poor service standards and lead to customer dissatisfaction.

Reactive: A reactive approach consists of resorting to a predetermined service recovery mechanism once a customer complains about poor service quality. It usually starts with apologizing to the customer and then taking steps to redeem the situation. The fundamental flaw with this approach is that, here the customer has already had a bad experience of the brand’s service. [Sources: Internet, Management Study Guide. Maintaining & Measuring Service Quality]

6. Analysis and Findings of Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction Level

Descriptive analysis and frequency distribution to analysis the despondence answer.

6.1 Descriptive Analysis:

6.1.1 It refers the transformation of raw data into a form and that will make them easy to understand and interpreted; rearranging, ordering manipulating data to provide descriptive information.

	Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	80	80	80	80
	Female	20	20	20	100
	Total	100	100	100	

Table: Gender Sample

Pie-Chart show participant’s Gender

Sample size is 100. Among them, there are 80% male and 20% female. The ratio can be seen graphically in the pie chart.

6.1.2 Age Group:

		Age		
Valid	15 - 25	70	70	70
	26 - 35	20	20	90
	More Than 35	10	10	100
Total		100	100	

Table: Age Group

Respondent's age group divided into four classes. Among them 15-25 years old are 70 peoples, 26-35 years old are 20 peoples and more than 35 years old are 10 peoples. So most of the respondents are between 15 – 25 years old. The ratio of the different age's group people are follows in bar chart.

Bar Chart: Respondents According to Age

6.1.3 Professional Group:

	Profession	Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Student	70	70	70	70
	Service Holder	20	20	20	90
	Business Person	10	10	10	100
Total		100	100	100	

Table: Professional Sample

Respondent's Profession group divided into three classes. Student 70%, Service Holder 20%, and Business Person 10%.The ratio of the different professions in the chart is covering students.

Pie-Chart show participant's Profession

6.2. Perception Statement in the Reliability Dimension

6.2.1. When Nijhoom Tours promise to do something by a certain time, it done so for its customers

	Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid
Valid	Strongly disagree	10	10%	10
	Disagree	14	14%	14
	Neutral	34	34%	34
	Agree	26	26%	26
	Strongly Agree	16	16%	16
Total		100	100%	100

Sample size was 100, with this statement most of the respondents were neutral. The numbers were 34, Here strongly agree were 16 and agree were 26 rest were, disagree and strongly disagree are the ratio between there is shown below in the bar chart. From the below diagram we can say that maximum number of the customer are dissatisfied because they do not keep their promise.

Chart: Nijhoom Tours promise to do something by a certain time

6.2.2 When you got a problem with Nijhoom Tours, solving the problem by the organization is very fast.

	Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid
Valid	Strongly disagree	08	08%	08
	Disagree	17	17%	17
	Neutral	25	25%	25
	Agree	35	35%	35
	Strongly Agree	15	15%	15
	Total	100	100%	100

Sample size was 100, with this statement most of the respondents were Agree. The numbers were 35, Here strongly agree were 15 and disagree were 17 rest were, disagree and strongly disagree were 08, the ratio between there is shown below in the bar chart. From the below diagram we can say that maximum number of the customer are satisfied because they solve problem very fast.

Chart: Nijhoom Tours solving the problem by them is very fast.

6.2.3 People like Nijhoom Tours

	Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid
Valid	Strongly disagree	08	08%	08
	Disagree	13	13%	13
	Neutral	12	12%	12
	Agree	46	46%	46
	Strongly Agree	21	21%	21
		Total	100	100%

Sample size was 100, with this statement most of the respondents were Agree. The numbers were 46, Here strongly agree were 21 and disagree were 13 rest were, disagree and strongly disagree were 08, the ratio between there is shown below in the bar chart. From the below diagram we can say that maximum number of the customer are like Nijhoom Tours brand.

Chart: People like Nijhoom Tour as Brand

6.2.4 Nijhoom Tour communicate with their customer after completed their course

	Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid
Valid	Strongly disagree	12	12%	12
	Disagree	16	16%	16
	Neutral	20	20%	20
	Agree	32	32%	32
	Strongly Agree	20	20%	20
		Total	100	100%

Sample size was 100, with this statement most of the respondents were Agree. The numbers were 32, Here strongly agree were 20 and disagree were 20 rest were, disagree and strongly disagree were 12, the ratio between there is shown below in the bar chart. From the below diagram we can say that maximum number of the customers are agree with their communication strategy.

Chart: Nijhoom Tour communicate with their customer instantly

6.3 Statement in the Responsiveness Dimension

6.3.1 The Sales people of Nijhoom Tour always help you to find the best services.

	Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid
Valid	Strongly disagree	18	18%	18
	Disagree	14	14%	14
	Neutral	20	20%	20
	Agree	24	24%	24
	Strongly Agree	24	24%	24
	Total	100	100%	100

Chart: The Sales person of Nijhoom Tour always help you to find the best services.

Sample size was 100, with this statement most of the respondents were Agree. The numbers were 48, Here strongly agree were 24 and disagree were 14 rest were, disagree and strongly disagree were 18, the ratio between there is shown below in the bar chart. From the below diagram we can say that maximum number of the customer are agree. Nijhoom Tour sales people always help the customers to find the best option or services.

6.3.2 Customer care department of Nijhoom Tours always respond rapidly

	Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid
Valid	Strongly disagree	12	12%	12
	Disagree	20	20%	20
	Neutral	26	26%	26
	Agree	22	22%	22
	Strongly Agree	20	20%	20
	Total	100	100%	100

Chart: Customer care department of Nijhoom Tour always respond rapidly

Sample size was 100, with this statement most of the respondents were Neutral. The numbers were 26, Here strongly agree were 20 disagree were 20 rest were, disagree and strongly disagree were 12, the ratio between there is shown below in the bar chart. From the below diagram we can say that maximum number of the customer are agree.

6.4 Statement in the Assurance Dimension

Nijhoom Tour employee’s behaviors for inspiring confidence on their services are very good.

	Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid
Valid	Strongly disagree	14	14%	14
	Disagree	10	10%	10
	Neutral	16	16%	16
	Agree	40	40%	40
	Strongly Agree	20	20%	20
	Total	100	100%	100

Chart: Customer care department of Nijhoom Tour always respond rapidly

Sample size was 100, with this statement most of the respondents were Agree. The numbers were 40, Here, strongly agree were 20 disagree were 10 rest were, disagree and strongly disagree were 14, the ratio between there is shown below in the bar chart. From the below diagram we can say that maximum number of the customer are agree about Nijhoom’s employee’s behaviors for inspiring confidence on their services are very good.

6.5 Statement in the Empathy Dimension

6.5.1 Nijhoom Tour understands your needs.

	Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid
Valid	Strongly disagree	12	12%	12
	Disagree	16	16%	16
	Neutral	20	20%	20
	Agree	32	32%	32
	Strongly Agree	20	20%	20
	Total	100	100%	100

Chart: Customer care department of Nijhoom's always respond rapidly

Sample size was 100, with this statement most of the respondents were Agree. The numbers were 32, Here strongly agree were 20 disagree were 16 rest were, disagree and strongly disagree were 12, the ratio between there is shown below in the bar chart. From the below diagram we can say that maximum number of the customer are neutral.

6.5.2 Nijhoom's services quality is good.

	Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid
Valid	Strongly disagree	10	10%	10
	Disagree	15	15%	15
	Neutral	25	25%	25
	Agree	35	35%	35
	Strongly Agree	15	15%	15
Total	100	100%	100	

Chart: Customer care department of Nijhoom's always respond rapidly

Sample size was 100, with this statement most of the respondents were Agree. The numbers were 35, Here strongly agree were 15 disagree were 15 rest were, disagree and strongly disagree were 10, the ratio between there is shown below in the bar chart. From the below diagram we can say that maximum number of the customers are satisfied and positive of Nijhoom's quality.

6.5.3 Nijhoom Tour is able to Meeting expectation of customers related to service quality.

	Position	Frequency	Percent	Valid
Valid	Strongly disagree	12	12%	12
	Disagree	20	20%	20
	Neutral	30	30%	30
	Agree	22	22%	22
	Strongly Agree	16	16%	16
	Total	100	100%	100

Sample size was 100, with this statement most of the respondents were Neutral. The numbers were 30, Here strongly agree were 160 disagree were 20 rest were, disagree and strongly disagree were 12, the ratio between there is shown below in the bar chart. From the below diagram we can say that maximum number of the customer are neutral.

Recommendations and Conclusion

Recommendations

1. Since Nijhoom Tours is a service-oriented organization, its business profit depends on its service quality. So the management of the company always should be aware about their service quality and performance, as service quality can lead to increased customer satisfaction and build strong brand image with good positioning.
2. The company should consider the factors to maintain service quality for a service firm is its ability to enhance customer positive feedback. Effectively managed customer feedback helps to create numerous opportunities for the development of interpersonal relationships between the customer and a firm's employees.
3. The Nijhoom Tours is a service providing firm where the completion of one process depends on another. Hence, lack of cooperation and cohesion should be minimized to provide prompt service. Different departments of the organization should work like a team to provide prompt and efficient services to the customers. This will ultimately help to offer consistent and reliable services where the employees will be more knowledgeable about what they are offering and how this should be proceeded on.

4. The behavior of employees should be modified enough through proper training to maintain positive attitude toward their job. They should always think of the firm as it is a fully service oriented one in which their attitudes are vital and can change the direction of the business to a great extent and build good image. They should remember it almost every time while at office or outside, so that they could be able to grow in terms of an empathic viewpoint.
5. The company should focus importantly on concentrated Marketing (one on one marketing) to explore and fulfill individual needs and wants of tourists.
6. Nijhoom Tour is leading company in the country in the industry sector. To survive with its leading position, the company should analyze the customer expectations first and then it should make a diagram so that the company can give the best services to the customers.

Conclusion

In the modern competitive environment, the pursuit of service quality is now considered to be an essential strategy. Offering a superior product is no longer sufficient, as firms in the 21st century economy compete on a much broader platform. In terms of the tour operation, service quality has become an increasingly important factor for its success and survival. From the analysis it is well observed that there is a considerable linkage existing between the perception of service quality and the performance of the organization. Most of the customers of an organization ask for more quality service, especially, quick and accurate service and good behavior from employees as they think a tour operating firm should provide such quality sufficiently. Travel and Tourism is a dynamic business. The Industry is beset by momentum changes in virtually every facet of industry activities. To achieve the objectives of Nijhoom Tour, it should work for improving the quality by identifying customer expectations as well as different problems related with management, employees and customers. To achieve this desired goal it has intention to pursuit of excellence in the climate of continuous improvement. Because it believes the line of excellence is never ending, it also believes that its strategic plans and business will its strengths in competitive environment. Its motto is providing every single customer services available in today's Tourism procedure for their customers.

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